

Comparative rate study on the acid and base catalyzed hydrolyses of formamide over a wide temperature range. Empirical relationship between k_H and k_{OH}

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Abstract : The hydrolysis of formamide is first order in [formamide] and in $[OH^-]$ or $[H^+]$. The values of rate constants for hydroxyl ion catalyzed hydrolysis, k_{OH} , in the temperature range 25–50 °C and those of hydrogen ion catalyzed, k_H , in the temperature range 25–65 °C are reported. The values of k_{OH} and k_H fit the empirical relationship : $k_{OH} = 2.8 \times 10^{-5} + (15.9 \pm 0.9) k_H$. Ignoring the intercept ($2.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), the ratio k_{OH}/k_H is found to be ~16. The values of activation parameters are : $\Delta H_{OH}^\ddagger = 57 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S_{OH}^\ddagger = -106 \pm 2 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (base hydrolysis) and $\Delta H_H^\ddagger = 73 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S_H^\ddagger = -88 \pm 4 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (acid hydrolysis).

Keywords : Formamide, acidic hydrolysis, basic hydrolysis, k_{OH}/k_H ratio.

Introduction

The kinetics and mechanism of the hydrolysis of amides has an important role in biochemistry^{1,2}. In particular, the hydrolysis of small amides has attracted much attention due its relevance to peptide. Formamide is implicated in prebiotic chemistry³. It has, therefore, been the subject of some theoretical and experimental studies^{1,2} including multiple isotopic⁴ and solvent isotopic⁵ effects. Its hydrolysis in strongly acidic⁶⁻⁹, strongly basic⁶ and buffered^{10,11} media in agreement with the rate laws (1), (2) and (3) respectively has been studied.

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_H [H^+] \quad (1)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_{OH} [OH^-] \quad (2)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_{OH} [OH^-] + k_H [H^+] + k_w \quad (3)$$

where k_{OH} , k_H and k_w are the rate constants for OH^- , H^+ and H_2O (neutral) catalyzed pathways, respectively. And k_{obs} is the experimental first order rate constants. Multiple isotopic effects¹⁰ and solvent isotopic effects¹¹ have also been studied.

Since our purpose was to obtain the empirical relationship between k_H and k_{OH} values at different temperature for formamide, we worked in strongly acidic and basic media (eqs. (1-2)) to obtain k_{OH} and k_H values independently. The other point of interest was to verify

the rate law (4) proposed earlier¹².

$$-d [\text{Amide}]/dt = k_{OH} [\text{Amide}] [OH^-] + k_{2OH} [\text{Amide}] [OH^-]^2 \quad (4)$$

Experimental

Formamide (Koch-light, AR) and all other chemicals of reagent grade were used and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The procedure for studying hydrolysis was based on well known Sorenson's formol titration method as described previously^{8,13,14}. The formamide was standardized by hydrolyzing its known amount and determining the ammonia content by formol titration. The reactions were conducted in stoppered conical flasks and the reactions were initiated by mixing temperature equilibrated (± 0.1 °C) solutions of formamide and sodium hydroxide/hydrochloric acid in desired proportions. In case of alkaline hydrolysis, the aliquot portions were withdrawn and added to the titration flasks containing ice cold formaldehyde and hydrochloric acid, the latter being equivalent to sodium hydroxide taken initially in any kinetics run. The contents were allowed to stay put for a minute and then titrated against standard NaOH. The same formol titration method was used in the study of acid hydrolysis using the procedure described earlier^{8,13,14}. In each case, ionic strength (1.0 mol L^{-1}) was adjusted with sodium chloride. The duplicate rate measurements were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

Results

Base hydrolysis :

The concentration of formamide was varied from 0.1 to 0.9 mol dm⁻³ at [NaOH] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, *I* = 1.0 mol dm⁻³. Using the initial rate method, an order of unity in [HCONH₂] was determined. Similarly, a variation in NaOH from 0.1 to 1.0 mol dm⁻³ at [HCONH₂] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³ and *I* = 1.0 mol L⁻¹ showed a clean-cut first order dependence on [OH⁻] also. The kinetics results are, therefore, in agreement with rate law (5).

$$-d[\text{Amide}]/dt = k_{\text{OH}} [\text{HOCONH}_2] [\text{OH}^-] \quad (5)$$

The value of second order rate constants, *k*_{OH}, obtained at different temperatures using appropriate forms of integrated second order equations are given in Table 1. Some experiments were made under pseudo-first order conditions with [OH⁻] in deficit. Values of *k*_{OH} determined directly and from pseudo-first order rate constant, *k*₁, are in excellent agreement (Table 1) with values determined under second order conditions. This rules out the

Table 1. Rate constants for alkaline hydrolysis of formamide at 25 °C

[Amide] (mol L ⁻¹)	[NaOH] (mol L ⁻¹)	<i>I</i> (mol L ⁻¹)	10 ³ <i>k</i> ₁ (s ⁻¹)	10 ³ <i>k</i> _{OH} (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
0.1	0.1	1.0	-	2.6
0.2	0.1	1.0	-	2.3
0.3	0.1	1.0	-	2.3
0.4	0.1	1.0	-	2.3
0.5	0.1	1.0	-	2.3
0.8	0.1	1.0	1.6	2.0
0.9	0.1	1.0	1.7	1.9
1.0	0.1	1.0	2.0	2.0
0.5	0.2	1.0	-	2.3
0.5	0.3	1.0	-	2.3
0.5	0.4	1.0	-	2.3
0.5	0.5	1.0	-	2.6
0.5	0.6	1.0	-	2.3
0.5	0.7	1.0	-	2.6
0.5	0.8	1.0	-	2.3
0.5	0.9	1.0	-	2.6
0.5	1.0	1.0	-	2.3
0.5	0.5	0.1	-	2.6
0.5	0.5	0.3	-	2.6
0.5	0.5	0.5	-	2.6
0.5	0.5	0.7	-	2.6
0.5	0.5	0.8	-	2.8
0.5	0.5	1.0	-	2.6

presence of *k*_{2OH} [Amide] [OH⁻]² term in the basic hydrolysis of formamide.

The reaction appears to be insensitive to variation in ionic strength (0.1–0.7 dm⁻³, Table 1). The activation parameters are given in Table 3.

Table 2. Second order rate constants for alkaline and acid hydrolysis of formamide at *I* = 1.0 mol L⁻¹

Amide	Temp. (°C)	10 ³ <i>k</i> _{OH} (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> _H (L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	<i>k</i> _{OH} / <i>k</i> _H
Formamide	25	2.4 ± 0.2	1.49 ± 0.1	16.1
Formamide	30	3.8 ± 0.2	2.30 ± 0.2	16.5
Formamide	35	6.0 ± 0.3	3.4 ± 0.2	17.6
Formamide	40	8.15 ± 0.4	5.9 ± 0.3	13.8
Formamide	45	12.5 ± 1.0	7.6 ± 0.5	16.4
Formamide	50	16.7 ± 1.0	10.3 ± 0.5	16.2
Formamide	55	-	29.0 ± 1.5	-
Formamide	60	-	37.5 ± 1.5	-
Formamide	65	-	57.0 ± 2.5	-
Ethanamide	65	0.634 ^a	2.06 ^a	3.1 ^a
Propanamide	65	-	-	2.0 ^a
<i>n</i> -Butanamide	65	-	-	2.0 ^a
<i>n</i> -Pentanamide	65	-	-	2.2 ^a
<i>n</i> -Hexanamide	65	-	-	1.7 ^a

^aRef. 15.

Table 3. Activation parameters of the alkaline and acid hydrolysis of amides

Amide	Δ <i>H</i> _H [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> _H [‡] (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Δ <i>H</i> _{OH} [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> _{OH} [‡] (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Formamide	73 ± 2 ^a	-88.0 ± 4 ^a	57 ± 2 ^a	-105.0 ± 2 ^a
Acetamide	82.3 ^b	-76.9 ^b	55.2 ^c	-141.7 ^c
Propanamide	75.6 ^b	-84.4 ^b	61.4 ^c	-124.1 ^c
<i>n</i> -Butanamide	79.0 ^b	-81.5 ^b	58.5 ^c	-137.5 ^c
<i>n</i> -Pentanamide	78.2 ^b	-83.6 ^b	60.6 ^c	-134.2 ^c

^aThis work. ^bRef. 17. ^cRef. 18.

Acid hydrolysis :

The acid hydrolysis of formamide has been studied earlier by us and is known to follow a second order kinetics, being first order with respect to [H⁺] and [HCONH₂] each. Using the procedure described earlier^{8,12,13}, the second order rate constants, *k*_H, at 5 °C interval in the temperature range 25–65 °C were determined and are given in Table 2. An earlier study by Rabinvitch and Winkler⁴ reports *k*_H values in the range 0–25 °C. Where-

ever, the results of this study overlap with those of the previous workers⁴, the agreement is excellent. For example our k_H value of $(1.49 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-4} \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 1.0 M and 25 °C is in good agreement with the value of $1.37 \times 10^{-4} \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ determined⁶ at 24.7 °C. It is gratifying to note that the k_H values reported for formamide¹³ by us have been validated subsequently by Miyakawa *et al.*⁹.

Discussion

The values of rate constants k_{OH} and k_H for formamide are given in Table 2. For comparison k_H and k_{OH} for some other amides are also given. The plot of k_{OH} versus k_H is for formamide is linear (Fig. 1) in agreement with the empirical eq. (6).

$$k_{OH} = 2.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} + (15.9 \pm 0.9) k_H \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1. The plot of k_{OH} versus k_H for the hydrolysis of formamide.

The value of intercept, $2.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, is within the experimental uncertainty ($\pm 5\%$) of the rate constants and hence can be ignored. Thus, k_{OH}/k_H can be taken equal to 15.9 ± 0.9 . The limited set of data for other alkyl amides show k_{OH}/k_H values to be relatively low¹⁵ and to lie between 1.4 and 3.1 (Table 2).

An examination of activation parameters (Table 3) shows the acid and basic hydrolyses of several alkyl amides to have nearly the same value of $\Delta H_H^\ddagger = 77.6 \pm 3.5$ and $\Delta H_{OH}^\ddagger = 58.5 \pm 2.5$, respectively. For acid hydrolysis, ΔS_H^\ddagger (82.9 ± 4.1) is also not much different for different amides including HCONH_2 . However, in case of basic hydrolysis, ΔS_{OH}^\ddagger value for formamide is much less negative than the values for all other amides. And this appears

to cause high k_{OH}/k_H ratio for HCONH_2 . In fact, a theoretical study is required to understand the cause of high k_{OH}/k_H ratio in case of formamide.

In OH^- catalysed reaction, the formation of transition state complex requires the attachment of an OH^- group on carbonyl carbon. The presence of an alkyl group appears to cause steric hindrance and require greater ordering. The replacement of H by alkyl group in CH_3CONH_2 appears to greatly reduce steric hindrance and ordering which is reflected in higher rate enhancement and less negative ΔS_{OH}^\ddagger for formamide. Incidentally, some what similar effects on rate and activation parameters have been noted in the HCHO-HSO_3^- and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHO-HSO}_3^-$ adduct formation reactions¹⁶ also.

The k_H/k_{OH} ratio reported here is useful in estimating the value of either of k_H and k_{OH} provided the other is known.

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References

1. G. I. Almerindo and J. R. Pliego (Jr.), *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **18**, 696; J. R. Pliego, *Chem. Phys.*, 2004, **306**, 273.
2. G. Estiu and K. M. Merz (Jr.), *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2007, **111**, 6507.
3. J. P. Krug, P. L. A. Popelier and R. F. W. Bader, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 7604.
4. J. F. Marlier, E. Campbell, C. Lai, M. Weber, L. A.

- Reinhardt and W. W. Cleland, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2006, **71**, 3829.
5. H. Slebocka-Tilk, A. A. Neveror and R. S. Brown, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 1851.
6. B. S. Rabinovitch and C. A. Winkler, *Can. J. Res.*, 1942, **20B**, 73.
7. V. K. Kriable and K. A. Holst, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 976.
8. S. Mittal, K. S. Gupta and Y. K. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 357; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 595; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 1220.
9. S. Miyakawa, H. J. Cleaves and S. L. Miller, *Origin Life Evol. Biosphere*, 2002, **32**, 195.
10. H. Slebocka-Tilk, F. Sauriol, M. Monette and R. S. Brown, *Can. J. Chem.*, 2002, **80**, 1343.
11. J. Hine, R. S. M. King, W. R. Midden and A. Sinha, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1981, **46**, 3186.
12. T. Yamana, Y. Mizakami, A. Tsuji, Y. Yasuda and K. Masuda, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1972, **20**, 881.
13. S. Mittal, K. S. Gupta and Y. K. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 827.
14. P. B. Hawk, "Practical Physiological Chemistry", P. Blackiston, Philadelphia, 1920, p. 525.
15. M. Willems and A. Bruylants, *Bull. Soc. Chem. Belges.*, 1951, **60**, 191.
16. T. Molson, S. D. Boyce and M. R. Hoffmann, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 2482.
17. T. Yamana, A. Tsuji and Y. Mizukami, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1972, **20**, 1229.
18. P. D. Bolton and G. L. Jackson, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, **24**, 969.